

**THE CURRENT STATE OF THE ART OF BAXSHI AND THE
DEGREE OF PRESERVATION OF TEACHER-DISCIPLE TRADITIONS**

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Annotation: In this article, we talk about the fact that the art of baxshi, which is a unique example of our nationality, is still valued and listened to by our people.

Keywords: baxshi, dombra, Sherna baxshi, Khoshbok Mardonakulov, teacher-student, inner voice.

In the XXI century, the spheres of culture and enlightenment are developing in the world. At the same time, attitudes and interests in folklore have changed. Especially in our Uzbekistan, exemplary work has been done in this direction. President Sh. Can you tell us about the results of Mirziyoyev's initiatives ?! The President said: "You all understand that if the body of society is the economy, it is the soul and the spirit. In building a new Uzbekistan, we need these two strong pillars, a strong economy based on market principles. and the rich heritage of our ancestors, a strong spirituality based on national and universal values "(Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Humanism, kindness and creativity are the foundation of our national idea. Tashkent: TASVIR Publishing House. 2021.). The reconstruction of the school of bakhshis in Termez, the establishment of bakhshi groups in schools of music and art are the product of new views on folk art. The decree to hold the International Festival of the Art of Bakhchisarai every two years was announced. Based on this, there is a need in our school to carefully study the history of teacher-student traditions in the field of folklore and folklore, to cover the life and creative work of bakhshis. Accordingly, in our writings we have written about the life and work of the People's Bakhshi of Uzbekistan Khushbok Mardonakul oglu. Bakhshi was born on December 25, 1942 in the village of Azon, Sherabad district, in the family of

Bakhshi-poet Mardonaqul Avliyokul oglu. As a child, he participated in various ceremonies with his father, studied the poems and epics recited by his father-in-law, and when the time came, took his father's drum in his hand and sang short songs. Whether it was in the blood of charity or not, it quickly began to catch the eye of the audience. He was also educated at a school in his village. After graduating from high school, he worked for some time in the school-educational offices of the collective farm.

However, the gift of giving did not leave his heart in peace. Finally, his passion for the art of baxshi led him to the Tashkent State Cultural and Educational College. He studied at this art school in 1963-1966 and worked in the department of culture of the district where he was born and grew up. received. He taught language and literature in schools, and at the same time became a master of his profession, working in the art of baxshi in the district department of culture. Following in the footsteps of their ancestors, they became famous bakhshis. In 2013, their selfless work paid off, and the title of People's Bakhshi of Uzbekistan was awarded.

"Currently, in Uzbek folklore, such schools of poetry and epic poetry as Bulungur, Kurgan, Shahrisabz, Kamay, Sherabad, southern Tajikistan, Khorezm have been identified as excellent centers of the art of baxshi."

Khushbok Mardonakul oglu also taught many traditional bakhshis in the Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions, where his grandfather Sherna was a poet and his father was a Mardonakul bakhshi. In particular, the students of the People's Bakhshis of Uzbekistan Bobaraim Mamatmurodov (deceased), Shoberdi Boltaev, Abdunazar Poyonov, Shodmon Khojamberdiyev, as well as Omondavlat Shernazarov, Zulhumor Shernazarova, Panji Tadjiev, Safar Poyonov (this list can be extended) He is actively involved in the day and is in the public eye. Bakhshi is pleased that his students are actively participating in all rounds and meetings. His disciples are also honoring their teacher. They remember and keep searching. If you are in Bakhshi's house, you will find yourself in a real Uzbek atmosphere. The courtyards are simple, just like the deals.

In an interview with Bakhshi, he said: "The tradition of bakhshi is that if a student does not follow the teacher, he will not be considered a student if he does not memorize epics and terms. He will stop. Why shouldn't the epic be lost? Because it reflects the people's hopes and aspirations. He must be a Chechen, a badass. He must lift the hero to the heavens and make the stars shine from the heavens. Only then will his Chechenness and generosity be revealed. . These were also simple descriptions reflected in the mirror of the bakhshi's heart. The enlightened bakhshi is still teaching his students the secrets of bakhshi. We wish the invincible will, perseverance and strength to accompany him on this path.

The poet is always creative. A pen in his hand, a book, a notebook, papers on a small sieve. Enlightenment seems to always shine in the heart of spirituality. It is as if nature has always endowed him with a stable, enduring creation. This means that the disciples will be noisy. Let's take another look at Bakhshi's past. From an early age, the team grew up telling stories. School, technical school, university, work in various fields of labor, living honestly with the couple, raising children with the participation of his hard work further invigorates the spirit of their growth and development. We will tell the exact story of a conversation. In 1968, Bakhshi married Oykhola, the daughter of a man named Toshtemir from the village of Sokhta in Sherabad. They washed, raised and brought up three sons (Saidmurad, Jurabek, Otabek) and five daughters (Gulnoz, Lola, Mohi, Qizlarbas, Dilafroz). The eldest son, Saidmurad, followed in the footsteps of his father and grandfather. He underwent many trials of witchcraft. When Saidmurod was sincere, the audience admired the melody of his drum and the clarity of his voice. Interestingly, although there is generosity in the blood of this dynasty, Saidmurod has heredity, but his two youngest sons, Jurabek and Otabek, do not have this ability and interest.

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